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Cultural trip to the countries of the former Yugoslavia

Fabio Rossano Dario^{1,2,a} & Maria Cristina Veiga De Vincenzo^{2,b}

¹ The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin,
Złocieniec, District Drawski, West Pomerania, Poland

² Ploaia Agronomia, Ecologia e Meio Ambiente,
Rua Leonardo Mota, 66 - São Paulo-SP, ZIP 05586-090, Brazil

^{a,b}E-mail address: fabiorossano@hotmail.com , crisvincenzo@hotmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This article includes notes and a photographic summary of scientific and touristic expeditions carried out in all the countries that once made up the former Yugoslavia. The aim was to explore the culture, architecture, and natural beauty of these countries: Slovenia, Croatia, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, and North Macedonia. The expeditions took place over three trips, totaling 48 days, during which we visited natural parks, historic cities, museums, and places of ecological, geological, landscape, historical, and architectural interest.

Keywords: Yugoslavia, Slovenia, Croatia, Serbia, tourism, environment

INTRODUCTION

The main objective of this scientific and touristic expedition was to explore the culture, architecture, and natural beauty of the countries that once made up the former Yugoslavia. The journey took place over three trips. The first, in October 2019, covered Croatia, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Montenegro. The second trip, in May 2022, was entirely dedicated to Slovenia, and the third trip, in September 2024, focused on North Macedonia. In total, the expedition lasted 48 days across these seven countries, during which we visited national parks, historic cities, museums, and sites of ecological, geological, landscape, historical, and architectural interest. Yugoslavia was a country in the Balkans and Central Europe that existed from 1918 to 1992. The concept of Yugoslavia, as a unified state for all South Slavic peoples – consisting of ethnic groups speaking Slavic languages and native to the South Slavic Balkan Peninsula, the Pannonian Plain, and the eastern Alps (Bulgarians, Serbs, Croats, Slavic Macedonians, Slovenes, Bosnians, and Montenegrins) – emerged at the end of the 17th century and gained prominence through the Illyrian Movement, initiated by Croatian writers in the 19th century. The name was created by combining the Slavic words *jug* ("south") and *slaveni* ("Slavs"). Efforts toward the formal creation of Yugoslavia accelerated after the Declaration of Corfu on July 20, 1917, an agreement between the Yugoslav Committee (composed largely of Croatian, Slovenian, and Bosnian Serb émigré politicians and political activists) and the government of the Kingdom of Serbia (then comprising parts of present-day Serbia and North Macedonia). Yugoslavia came into existence in 1918 after the First World War, under the name Kingdom of Serbs, Croats, and Slovenes, formed through the merger of the Kingdom of Serbia with the provisional State of Slovenes, Croats, and Serbs. This union represented the first sovereign state for the South Slavic peoples after centuries of foreign rule in the region under the Ottoman Empire and Austria-Hungary. The kingdom gained international recognition on July 13, 1922, at the Conference of Ambassadors in Paris. On October 3, 1929, the state's official name was changed to the Kingdom of Yugoslavia.

The Kingdom was invaded by Axis powers on April 6, 1941. In 1943, a Federal Democratic Yugoslavia was proclaimed by the Yugoslav communist resistance. Yugoslavia was renamed the Federal People's Republic of Yugoslavia in 1945 when a communist government was established. The Partisan leader, Josip Broz Tito (1892–1980), ruled the country from 1944 as Prime Minister and later as President until his death in 1980. In 1963, the country was renamed for the final time as the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia.

Figure 1. Location of the former Yugoslavia. Source: Geographic Guide <https://www.guiageo-europa.com/mapas/yugoslavia.htm>

The six constituent republics that made up the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia were Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, and Slovenia. Following an economic and political crisis in the 1980s, Yugoslavia split along the borders of its republics, initially into five countries, leading to the Yugoslav Civil War. After the dissolution, the republics of Montenegro and Serbia formed a smaller federal state, the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia, which was known as Serbia and Montenegro from 2003 to 2006. This state was dissolved in 2006 when Montenegro and Serbia became independent countries. Today, the former Yugoslavia consists of six countries: Slovenia, Croatia, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, and North Macedonia. Bosnia and Herzegovina is divided into two political entities: the Republika Srpska and the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Slovenia

The Republic of Slovenia has a territory 16 times smaller than Poland (20,271 km²) and a population of approximately 2 million inhabitants. It is located in a region commonly classified as Eastern Europe and borders Italy, Austria, Hungary, and Croatia. Slovenia's geography is characterized by a mountainous region formed by the Alps, caves, and extensive

vegetation. It also has a small coastline along the Adriatic Sea. The main rivers in Slovenia are the Sava and the Drava. Slovenia is a developed and industrialized nation. Its economy is highly diversified and includes a strong industrial sector. The primary sector is notable for the production of fruits, milk, and meat.

Ljubljana is the capital and largest city of Slovenia, and arguably one of the most beautiful cities in Europe: everything is stunning, clean, and well-organized. The Dragon Bridge (*Zmajski Most*) is the city's symbol, built in the “Viennese Secession” style at the beginning of the 20th century, during a time when Ljubljana was part of the Austro-Hungarian Empire. The bridge features four large dragon statues, one at each corner, each representing a mother dragon with four offspring (**Photos 1, 2**).

The Ljubljana dragon symbolizes strength and courage and has its origins in the legend of Jason and the Argonauts:

“The Greek hero Jason and his fellow Argonauts traveled to Colchis (present-day Georgia and Abkhazia), where they stole the 'Golden Fleece' (the golden wool of the winged ram Chrysolmalus). Aboard the ship *Argo*, they fled their pursuers but found themselves at the mouth of the Danube River instead of heading south to the Aegean Sea and their Greek homeland. With no way to turn back, they continued along the Danube and then the Ljubljanica River. They stopped at the source of the Ljubljanica, where they spent the winter. In the spring, they dismantled the *Argo*, carried it on their shoulders to the Adriatic coast, rebuilt it, and continued their journey.

According to legend, upon arriving in the area between what is now Vrhnika and Ljubljana, the Argonauts crossed a large lake surrounded by a swamp. In the swamp lived a terrible dragon, which Jason heroically killed after a fierce battle. This monster became the Ljubljana dragon.”

We walked along the banks of the Ljubljanica River to admire the beautiful scenery, crossing the bridges that span the river, such as the Triple Bridge, which has been rebuilt several times, initially constructed from wood in 1280. These three bridges connect the modern part of the city to the medieval part.

The Shoemakers' Bridge was historically a site where Christians tortured heretics during the Middle Ages. We also passed through Prešeren Square, the most important square in the city, named after the Slovenian Romantic poet France Prešeren (1800–1849).

A particularly curious detail in this square: a statue of the poet Prešeren is positioned to gaze at the window of the building where his muse, Julija Primic (1816–1864), once lived (**Photos 3–8**).

We visited the Central Market, designed by architect Jože Plečnik (1872–1957) in 1931. Plečnik is considered the greatest Slovenian architect of all time, and his works can be found not only in Ljubljana, his hometown, but also in other cities such as Vienna, Belgrade, and Prague.

At the Church of Saint Nicholas, Ljubljana Cathedral, you can see pagan symbols carved into the door. Ljubljana Castle is a constant presence in the city's landscape, as it is situated on one of the hills surrounding the city, close to the center.

Access to the castle is possible by walking along a road or by taking the funicular. Originally, it was a medieval fortress built in the 11th century and rebuilt over the centuries until its completion in the 15th century (**Photos 9, 10**).

A self-declared "Autonomous Culture Zone," Metelkova Mesto occupies a former military barracks, originally commissioned by the Austro-Hungarian army in 1882 and

completed in 1911. In this vibrant neighborhood, home to university students and bohemians, you'll find several clubs, live music venues, art galleries, artists' studios, sculptures in the gardens, and surrealist paintings covering the walls of the buildings. This is the coolest district in the city, and it has been declared a cultural heritage site (**Photos 11, 12**).

The Natural History Museum of Slovenia, the oldest Slovenian cultural and scientific institution, boasts rich and beautiful collections of animals, fossils, and minerals that demonstrate changes in biodiversity, the development of natural history thinking, and various collection techniques and sample preparation methods. One of the museum's main attractions and symbols is an almost complete skeleton of a woolly mammoth (*Mammuthus primigenius*), one of the best-preserved specimens in Europe (**Photos 13-16**).

Revolution Square, designed by architect Edvard Ravnikar (1907–1993), is one of the monumental works of concrete architecture from the former Yugoslavia. The main monument in the square is the Monument to the Revolution (*Spomenik Revolucije*), which was opened in 1975 and created by Drago Tršar (1927–2023) (**Photos 17, 18**). These works from the communist period of Yugoslavia are known as Socialist Realism. Between 1950 and 1970, Tito ordered the construction of massive structures known as *spomenik* (monuments, in Serbian-Croatian). Designed by Yugoslav sculptors and architects such as Dušan Džamonja (1928–2009), Vojin Bakić (1915–1992), and Bogdan Bogdanović (1922–2010), these monuments were erected to honor places that housed concentration camps or where important battles of World War II took place. At the same time, they symbolize the strength, power, resistance, and suffering of the heroic Slavic people who fought against Nazism.

Approximately 50 km from Ljubljana is the city of Bled, located in the Upper Carniola region. Bled is known for its beautiful lake, surrounded by the Julian Alps, forests, and a medieval castle. Lake Bled encircles Bled Island (*Blejski otok*), which features a few buildings, the main one being the pilgrimage church dedicated to the Assumption of Mary (*Cerkev Marijinega vnebovzetja*), built in the 17th century and decorated with remnants of 15th-century Gothic frescoes.

We circled Lake Bled along a 6 km trail, offering beautiful views of the island and the castle. The surrounding area is entirely wooded, with fir, oak, ash, maple, horse chestnut, and primarily linden (*Tilia cordata*) and beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) trees (**Photos 19–22**).

Next, we climbed the Ojstrica trail to enjoy the "classic view" of the lake, which often appears on postcards of the city. Bled Castle is the oldest in Slovenia and began to be built in the 11th century on a 130-meter-high cliff on the shores of the lake. In addition to the stunning view of the lake, the castle houses a small but interesting ethnology museum (**Photos 23, 24**).

In just a few minutes by car, you reach the beautiful medieval city of Radovljica (**Photo 25**), known as the world capital of honey, produced by Carniolan bees (*Apis mellifera carnica*), a species endemic to Slovenia. We bought this delicious honey and tried traditional Slovenian sweets: Kremšnita (a traditional pie made with crispy puff pastry and vanilla cream) and Potica (a whole wheat cake made with walnuts).

Not far from Bled is the picturesque village of Spodnja Sorica, considered the most beautiful in Slovenia, where the Impressionist painter Ivan Grohar (1867–1911) was born (**Photo 26**). Also nearby is Škofja Loka, a UNESCO World Heritage site, regarded as one of the most beautiful medieval cities in Slovenia (**Photos 27, 28**).

Triglav National Park (*Triglavski Narodni Park* in Slovenian) is the only national park in Slovenia and one of the oldest and largest national parks in Europe [1]. It was established in its modern form in 1981, when Slovenia was part of the Socialist Republic of Yugoslavia (**Photo**

29). Mount Triglav, which gives its name to the park, is the highest peak of the Julian Alps. From it, the valleys spread out radially, supplying water to two large river systems: the Soča and the Sava [2–6].

The Soča River is a true gem of the Julian Alps and one of the most beautiful rivers in Europe. It flows past the towns of Bovec, Kobarid, Tolmin, Kanal ob Soči (**Photo 30**), Nova Gorica, and Gorizia, entering the Adriatic Sea near the town of Monfalcone. Due to the color of its waters, the river is known as "the emerald beauty" (**Photo 31**). It is said to be one of the few rivers in the world that retains such a color throughout its length. The river is also well known for the marble trout (*Salmo marmoratus*), a species endangered due to the introduction of non-indigenous trout species such as brown trout (*Salmo trutta*).

The Sava River is the longest tributary of the Danube, nearly a thousand kilometers long. It flows through Slovenia, Croatia, along the border with Bosnia and Herzegovina, and finally reaches Serbia, where it meets the Danube in the charming capital, Belgrade. The Sava River is formed by the confluence of the Sava Dolinka (**Photo 32**) and the Sava Bohinjka headwaters, where it discharges into the Sava Dolinka [7].

Mount Triglav, at 2,864 meters, is the highest summit of the Julian Alps and Slovenia (**Photo 33**). It is a national symbol and is included in the flag of the Republic of Slovenia (**Photo 34**). Triglav National Park is an area of varied relief, manifested in a wealth of natural features: crystal-clear water, forests, high-altitude ridges, valleys, mountain lakes, and bogs (**Photos 35, 36**). Lake Bohinj is the largest natural lake in Slovenia (**Photo 37**). It is located in a glacially formed basin and is home to 53 species of planktonic algae, around 60 species of invertebrate fauna, and at least 16 species of fish. Besides the lake, St. John the Baptist Church is the hallmark of Bohinj. This medieval church and stone bridge are over 700 years old, spanning periods from Romanticism to Baroque (**Photo 38**).

Zelenci Springs is a nature reserve near the town of Kranjska Gora. It is the source of the Sava Dolinka River. At Zelenci Springs, water from the underground Nadiža Creek re-emerges through the porous bottom of a 2-meter-deep lake, whose waters are noted for their deep, brilliant green [8] (**Photo 39**). The surroundings of the spring support plant life adapted to riparian habitats with damp soils: alder (*Alnus glutinosa*), willows (*Salix fragilis*), and an assortment of flowering plants such as bogbean (*Menyanthes trifoliata*), marsh arrowgrass (*Triglochin palustris*), marsh lousewort (*Pedicularis palustris*), and white butterbur (*Petasites albus*), a flowering plant species in the family Asteraceae (**Photo 40**).

Located just 2 km from Kranjska Gora, Lake Jasna is a beautiful alpine lake surrounded by mountains. The lake is guarded by a statue of a Zlatorog (golden horn), the mythical chamois of Mt. Triglav (**Photo 41**). The Peričnik Waterfall, with a height of 52 meters, is one of the highest waterfalls in Slovenia. Powerful karst springs rise from valley bottoms, and where water drops over a ledge, a waterfall is created. Springs flow into streams that can erode deeply into the surface, creating steep mountain ravines, gorges, canyons, and troughs. The spectacular Vintgar Gorge is 1,600 meters long and is located 4 km from the center of Bled. Trails, narrow passages, and bridges lead visitors to the end of the gorge, which is marked by the magnificent 16-meter-high Šum Waterfall, the highest fluvial waterfall in Slovenia (**Photos 42-45**). The Tolmin Gorge, in the Soča Valley, is situated about 180 meters above sea level. The wild water channels, with their typical breakings, are seen as smooth vertical rocks, formed by the engraving of the Tolminka River into the limestone. The Zadlaščica River has excavated water channels through depth erosion (**Photo 46**).

Slovenia is the land of beekeeping, with a rich tradition deeply rooted in the people's consciousness. It is home to the Carniolan honeybee, an indigenous bee species. Painted beehive panels are a distinctive feature of Slovenian beekeeping and a manifestation of folk art (**Photo 47**). The Carniolan honeybee (*Apis mellifera carnica*) is a subspecies of the western honeybee that has naturalized and adapted to the Kočevje region (a sub-region of Carniola) in Slovenia, the southern part of the Austrian Alps, the Dinarides region, the southern Pannonian plain, and the northern Balkans. Today, this subspecies is the second most popular among beekeepers, after the Italian bee. It is favored for several reasons: its ability to defend itself effectively against insect pests while being extremely gentle in its behavior toward beekeepers. These bees are particularly skilled at adjusting worker populations in response to nectar availability [9].

Near Kobarid, above the emerald-green Soča River, lies the gorge of the Kozjak stream, where the 15-meter-high Kozjak Waterfall particularly stands out. A footpath leads to the waterfall, with small wooden bridges in some areas. The path ends at a terrace with a mystical view of the rocky amphitheater, featuring a green pool and a white beam of water (**Photos 48-50**).

The most characteristic tree species in Triglav National Park are beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) (**Photo 51**) [12], spruce (*Picea excelsa*), and larch (*Larix decidua*). Although the Alpine environment is typically associated with larch, spruce, and dwarf pines, stands of thermophilous hop hornbeam (*Ostrya carpinifolia*) and dwarf ash are common features of the Julian Alps. The flora of Triglav National Park is very rich and diverse. In Slovenia, the Siberian iris (*Iris sibirica*) is a common plant species found in wet meadows, which may occasionally be flooded (**Photo 52**) [11].

The fauna of Triglav National Park, which represents its wildlife, is extremely rich and diverse due to the conservation and sustainability of its habitat. The fire salamander (*Salamandra salamandra*) is the most common species of salamander seen in springtime. It is black with yellow spots, and this conspicuous coloration serves to deter predators by signaling its toxicity [12]. Reptiles in Triglav National Park are represented by several interesting species of lizards, such as *Zootoca vivipara* (common lizard), *Lacerta viridis* (European green lizard), *Lacerta bilineata* (western green lizard), *Podarcis muralis* (common wall lizard), and *Iberolacerta horvathi* (Horvath's rock lizard). *Podarcis muralis* is a lizard species with a wide distribution across Europe. It prefers rocky environments, including urban areas, where it can scurry between rocks and rubble. Its small scales vary greatly in color and pattern, typically brownish or greyish, with occasional green tinges [13] (**Photos 53, 54**). *Zootoca vivipara* is the only reptile that lives at the top of mountains and in the northern regions of Europe [14], but it can also be seen in Triglav National Park. The Horvath's rock lizard is native to northwestern Croatia, Slovenia, and the adjoining parts of northeastern Italy and southern Austria. It is a rock specialist and is very agile, even leaping into the air to catch prey.

Among the mammals recorded in Triglav National Park are *Ursus arctos* (brown bear) [15], *Canis lupus* (wolf), *Lynx lynx* (lynx), *Meles meles* (badger), *Martes foina* (bee-eater), *Martes martes* (pine marten), *Vulpes vulpes* (red fox), *Marmota marmota* (marmot), *Lutra lutra* (otter), *Capreolus capreolus* (roe deer), *Capra hircus* (goat), *Capra ibex* (Alpine ibex), *Cervus elaphus* (elk), and *Rupicapra rupicapra* (chamois). Slovenia's diverse landscapes and climates offer a lot to ornithologists and amateur bird watchers alike. So far, 386 bird species have been recorded in Slovenia, many of these naturally occurring species in Triglav National Park (**Photos 55, 56**) [16-23], such as *Fringilla coelebs* (common chaffinch), *Loxia curvirostra* (red

crossbill), *Garrulus glandarius* (Eurasian jay), *Corvus corax* (common raven), *Buteo buteo* (common buzzard), *Prunella collaris* (Alpine accentor), *Motacilla alba* (white wagtail), *Motacilla cinerea* (mountain wagtail), *Anas platyrhynchos* (mallard), *Mergus merganser* (goosander), *Pernis apivorus* (European honey buzzard), *Dendrocopos major* (great spotted woodpecker), *Erithacus rubecula* (robin), *Carduelis carduelis* (European goldfinch), *Phalacrocorax carbo* (great cormorant), *Mergus merganser* (merganser), *Parus major* (great tit), *Poecile montanus* (mountain titmouse), *Turdus merula* (common blackbird), *Turdus philomelos* (song thrush), *Passer domesticus* (house sparrow), *Hirundo rustica* (barn swallow), *Ciconia nigra* (black stork), *Asio flammeus* (short-eared owl), *Ardea cinerea* (common heron), *Coloeus monedula* (western jackdaw), and *Cyanistes caeruleus* (Eurasian blue tit).

In the Kras region, in southwestern Slovenia, lies Postojna Cave, the largest tourist cave in Europe, which has been visited since 1818 and can be explored through 5 km of tunnels and underground galleries. It is the most visited cave in the world and the birthplace of caving, thanks to the proteus salamander (*Proteus anguinus*), a blind amphibian endemic to this cave, known as the "dragon's baby." The olm or proteus "is the largest known troglobitic vertebrate, with a lifespan of over 100 years. It is the top predator of aquatic cave communities, highly vulnerable and a sensitive bio-indicator of habitat-changing human activities" [24]. The cave is home to some of the best examples of karst formations, with large numbers of stalagmites and stalactites in a wide range of shapes and sizes (**Photo 57**). Close to the cave is the stunning Predjama Castle, set into a mountain, built in the 13th century on a cliff (**Photo 58**).

The Slovenian coastline is quite narrow and comprises the regions of Goriška and Slovenian Istria, along the Adriatic Sea. Koper is the largest port city in Slovenia and was under the rule of the Republic of Venice for almost five centuries (**Photos 59-61**). Portorož is an elegant resort in Slovenia, with excellent infrastructure for tourists (**Photos 62, 63**). Piran is a beautiful city on the Slovenian coast, dating back to the Roman period, surrounded by a wall built in the 7th century, offering incredible views of the Adriatic coast (**Photos 64-66**). In addition to these three beautiful and historic cities, we couldn't miss visiting the Sečovlje Salina in the Sečovlje Salina Nature Park. It is the oldest active salt mine in the world, with the earliest record being a decree by Charlemagne from 804 (**Photos 67, 68**).

Heading to Maribor, in the northeast of Slovenia, between Austria, Hungary, and Croatia, two cities are worth visiting: Celje and Ptuj, both ancient Roman cities. Celje, the ancient Celeia of the Romans, is located at the confluence of four rivers, giving it strategic importance. In the central square of Celje, there is a statue honoring the remarkable Alma Karlin (1889-1950), who was born and died in this city and was the first woman to travel around the world (**Photos 69-71**). Ptuj, the ancient Roman Petóvio, is very charming, overlooking the Drava River, with colorful buildings, a beautiful tower, and a stunning medieval castle from the 12th century (**Photos 72-76**).

Maribor is one of the most beautiful cities in Europe, very welcoming, with medieval buildings, squares, and wooded gardens (**Photos 77-82**). The banks of the Drava River, a tributary of the Danube, are entirely wooded. The Drava is crossed by the Old Bridge (Stari Most), made entirely of iron and painted red, built in 1913 and historically marked by Hitler's records in the city (**Photo 83**). In a building on the bank of the Drava River, there is a vine with nearly 500 years of historical record, having survived the wars and plagues that devastated Europe in recent centuries. The building where the vine grows is a historic structure known as the Old Vine House. The vine produces an annual harvest of around 35 to 55 kg of grapes, enough to make 15 to 35 liters of wine, which is bottled in specially designed bottles created

by Slovenian industrial designer Oskar Kogoj (**Photos 84, 85**). There are several ways to admire the oldest vine in the world. One of them is by drinking a white Muscat wine at a bar next to the Old Vine House.

In Castle Square stands the *spomenik NOB* (National Liberation) monument, a 7-meter-high bronze sculpture that strongly resembles the inverted view of a dripping drop of water. It features the faces of hundreds of people who were victims of Nazism, along with excerpts from farewell letters, such as that of Partizan Jože Fluks (**Photo 86**). The *spomenik* is the work of Maribor-born sculptor Slavko Tihec (1928-1993) and was created in honor of the 667 Slovenian communists who were killed by German forces during the War of National Liberation (World War II) for attempting to resist the Nazi occupation.

The Maribor Botanical Garden is a great option for a peaceful walk among woods and gardens, featuring collections of ornamental plants used in beekeeping and folk medicine. It is located on an archaeological site, an ancient Iron Age cemetery, with Viking-style tombs made of dome-shaped earth and stacked stones (**Photos 87-89**).

Croatia

The Republic of Croatia is an Eastern European country with a long coastline along the Adriatic Sea. It encompasses more than a thousand islands and is traversed by the Dinaric Alps. Croatia borders Hungary and most of the countries that once formed Yugoslavia: Slovenia, Serbia, Montenegro, the Republic of Srpska, and Bosnia and Herzegovina, as well as having a maritime border with Italy in the Gulf of Trieste. Its continental territory is divided into two parts by the port of Neum in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Croatia has the second-largest territory of the former Yugoslav republics, covering 56,594 km², and a population of approximately 4 million people.

Croatia's economy is primarily based on a diverse range of services and industries, particularly in the chemical, naval, and metal-mechanical sectors. Tourism is a major source of income, with the country ranking among the 20 most popular tourist destinations in the world.

Zagreb is the capital of Croatia, located between the banks of the Sava River and the slopes of Mount Medvednica. The city is known for its beautiful buildings, museums, galleries, and monuments, with a strong influence of Austro-Hungarian architecture from the 18th and 19th centuries. The historic part of the city, including the Upper Town and Kaptol, is the main attraction, featuring historic buildings, churches, restaurants, and cafes. The Lower Town is home to Ban Jelačić Square, and the upper part can be reached via a funicular or by walking along Tomićeva Street. The Upper Town is home to the Gothic-style Zagreb Cathedral with its two towers and the Church of Saint Mark, which dates back to the 13th century and features a colorful tiled roof. Nearby is the pedestrian street Tkalčićeva, lined with cafes (**Photos 90-93**).

Through the Stone Gate in the Upper Town is Zagreb's oldest pharmacy, dating back to the 14th century, where Dante Alighieri's great-grandson worked as a pharmacist. The Lotrščak Tower, built in the 13th century, is one of the best-preserved buildings from the city's ancient defense system. This medieval tower is located in the heart of the city, close to St. Mark's Square. Every day, at noon sharp, a cannon is fired from the top of the tower. The tradition began in the 19th century to mark midday for the city's inhabitants (**Photo 94**).

We leave the historic center and head to a place known as "The Green Horseshoe." The green corridor resembles the shape of a horseshoe, hence the name. It is a vast complex of interconnected squares and parks in the heart of Zagreb, with beautiful buildings such as

museums, banks, theaters, libraries, palaces, and a botanical garden, which is worth a visit. There is also the train station (Glavni Kolodvor), famous for being mentioned by Agatha Christie in *Murder on the Orient Express*. In fact, the murder probably occurred on the stretch between Zagreb and Slavonski Brod. Next to the train station is the iconic Hotel Esplanade, built to accommodate passengers on the Orient Express, which ran between Paris and Istanbul (**Photos 95-100**).

The Croatian National Theatre, a neo-baroque architectural marvel that opened in 1895, is the symbol of Marshal Tito Square (**Photo 101**). The Austro-Hungarian Emperor Franz Joseph I attended the inauguration of the theater during his visit to the city in 1895. International artists, including Franz Liszt and Richard Strauss, have performed at this theater. At the entrance to the theater is the "Well of Life" mural fountain, designed by Croatian artist and sculptor Ivan Meštrović (1883-1962).

A bronze statue of Nikola Tesla (1856-1943), regarded as one of the greatest inventors of all time, stands on a public sidewalk. Tesla was Serbian but was born in a small town in Croatia. This genius invented the radio, the incandescent lamp, the electromagnetic induction motor, created the first X-ray image, and perfected fluorescent lamps. Tesla is often called an "unjust genius" for not receiving proper credit for many of his inventions, including the incandescent lamp and the use of alternating current to transmit electrical energy over long distances, which is used in high-voltage power lines and was patented by North American businessman Thomas Edison.

Plitvice Lakes National Park is known for its natural beauty. Situated on the Bosnia and Herzegovina border, about halfway between Zadar and Zagreb, it is the jewel of mountainous central Croatia and was registered as a UNESCO World Heritage site in 1979. It is the oldest national park in Southeast Europe, established in 1949 when Yugoslavia still existed. The protected area spans 296.85 square kilometers [25]. Plitvice Lakes are located in the forested mountainous region of Croatia and are world-famous for their sixteen lakes arranged in cascades. These lakes were formed by the confluence of several small rivers and subterranean karst rivers [26]. The Plitvice Lakes National Park features large forest complexes, with lakes and waterfalls stretching between them, along which there are many forest paths and wooden bridges, lakes, and small streams. Numerous wooden footbridges and pathways wind over the lakes and around their shores, creating gentle trails for visitors to wander, explore, and take in the views (**Photos 102, 103**).

In Plitvice Lakes, the tufa-formation process, in which tufa barriers form and grow, is a highly complex process that has created the cascade lake system. This process involves several physiochemical and biological factors (**Photos 104-110**). Tufa, also called travertine [27], is a variety of limestone formed when carbonate minerals precipitate out of water at ambient temperatures. The lakes of Plitvice are all interconnected and follow the flow of water, separated by natural dams of travertine, which is deposited by the action of moss, algae, and bacteria. The particularly sensitive travertine barriers are the result of an interplay between water, plants, and air. Encrusted plants and bacteria accumulate on top of each other, forming travertine barriers that grow at a rate of about 1 cm per year [28-36]. The lakes are renowned for their distinctive colors, which range from azure to green, grey, or blue. These colors change constantly, depending on the number of minerals or organisms in the water and the angle of sunlight.

More than 1,400 plant taxa (species and subspecies) have been recorded in Plitvice Lakes National Park, which amounts to 30% of the entire Croatian flora. This can be explained by its

specific geographic location, as well as by geomorphological, climatological, and ecological factors. The beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) is the predominant tree species in the park [10]. Because beech trees live for such long periods, they provide gnarled and knotted habitats for some deadwood specialists, such as hole-nesting birds and wood-boring insects. The bark is often home to a variety of fungi, mosses, and lichens [31]. The European silver fir (*Abies alba*) is a large evergreen coniferous tree, growing 40-50 m tall. As a long-lived tree, the fir is considered a significant ecological and functional species that stabilizes soils and retains water. Both fir and beech, as the main coexisting species in montane mixed-species forests, are shade-tolerant and can thrive under deep shade for extended periods [32-34].

Bog habitats and their vegetation in Croatia, as well as in the park, are relics of the glacial period. They are found in small areas and are highly dependent on microclimatic conditions. Highly specialized and very rare plant species, now endangered, depend on this type of habitat: peat moss (*Sphagnum* sp.), the common sundew (*Drosera rotundifolia*), the common butterwort (*Pinguicula vulgaris*), the lesser bladderwort (*Utricularia minor*), and many other species [35]. These species are at risk of extinction due to specific conditions and can only be preserved through active protective measures (maintaining a favorable water regime and removing some of the vegetation). In addition to plant and animal species, the park is also abundant in fungi species.

The fauna, which represents the wildlife of Plitvice Lakes, is extremely rich and diverse due to the conservation and sustainability of the habitat. There are many species of insects, including 321 species of butterflies. Other interesting insects include the Trichoptera, which contains a specific endemic species, and the Carabidae (an important family of beetles), which are excellent indicators of habitat quality [36]. The most common fish species in Plitvice Lakes are the chub (*Squalius cephalus*) (**Photo 111**), Neretva roach (*Rutilus pigus*), Marsilijev pijor (*Phoxinus phoxinus*), crvenperka (*Scardinius erythrophthalmus*), and trout [37]. In the Plitvice Lakes National Park, there are 14 species of amphibians and 14 species of reptiles. Some of the interesting lizard species include *Zootoca vivipara* (common lizard) and *Iberolacerta horvathi* (Horvath's rock lizard). *Zootoca vivipara* is the only reptile that lives at the tops of mountains and in the far north of Europe [38], but it can also be found in the park.

The ornithofauna of the Plitviče Lakes is rich and diverse, comprising 168 bird species (**Photo 112**). Due to the preservation and size of the forest habitats, there is great diversity and abundance of species associated with forest environments. Some of the most interesting species include *Buteo buteo* (common buzzard), *Asio otus* (long-eared owl), *Strix uralensis* (Ural owl), *Strix aluco* (brown owl), *Glaucidium passerinum* (Eurasian pygmy owl), *Aegolius funereus* (boreal owl), *Erithacus rubecula* (robin) (**Photo 113**), *Cinclus cinclus* (white-throated dipper), *Poecile palustris* (marsh tit), and *Motacilla cinerea* (mountain wagtail). There are over 50 mammal species registered in the Plitviče Lakes National Park, most of which are bats [39-41]. Among the large mammals recorded in the park are *Ursus arctos* (brown bear), *Canis lupus* (wolf), *Lynx lynx* (lynx), *Meles meles* (badger), *Martes martes* (pine marten), and *Lutra lutra* (otter). The otter (*Lutra lutra*) and lynx (*Lynx lynx*) are on the endangered species list [42-50].

The coast of Croatia is recognized as one of the most beautiful places in the world, with landscapes colored by the turquoise blue sea, filled with paradisiacal islands and beautiful historic cities featuring impressive architecture – all in perfect harmony. Excellent restaurants offer incredibly delicious and healthy cuisine, and the Croatian people are very polite. Additionally, cats can always be found roaming freely through the streets, climbing on the roofs of houses. We chose three cities to visit: Dubrovnik, Split, and Trogir.

The fortified city of Dubrovnik, a UNESCO World Heritage site and formerly the Republic of Ragusa, deserves the title "the pearl of the Adriatic" because it is surreally beautiful and perfect from both an aesthetic and architectural standpoint. The city, overlooking the Adriatic Sea, is surrounded by walls and fortifications built between the 13th and 16th centuries. You can walk almost 2 km along the wall, with incredible views of the sea and the city, and climb the Tower of Minčeta, the highest point of the city's walls. From there, you have a beautiful view of the Lovrijenac Fortress, a symbol of resilience for the people of Dubrovnik. This important fortress, which protected the city for hundreds of years, earned the nickname "Gibraltar of Dubrovnik" due to its dramatic location on a rock jutting out toward the Adriatic Sea (**Photos 114-135**).

Dubrovnik was once one of the most important republics in the Mediterranean, known at the time as the Republic of Ragusa, founded in the 7th century. The city is renowned for pioneering public institutions, with the first medical service dating back to 1301, the first pharmacy still in operation since 1317, an old people's home founded in 1347, the first quarantine hospital, opened in 1377, the first orphanage, opened in 1432, and a water supply system, 20 km long, built in 1436.

Among the historical and architectural attractions, we visited the Pile Gate, the main entrance to the city, built in 1537; the Museum of the 17th-century poet Marin Držić (1508-1567), considered one of the best Renaissance playwrights and prose writers in Croatian literature; the Maritime Museum; the Franciscan Museum, where one of the oldest pharmacies in Europe, dating from 1317, is still in operation; and the Jesuit Stairs, designed in 1738 by the Italian Pietro Passalacqua, who was inspired by the Piazza di Spagna in Rome. The stairs became famous in the *Game of Thrones* series during the "Walk of Shame," in which Queen Cersei Lannister, a fictional character from *A Song of Ice and Fire* by George R.R. Martin, descended the steps completely naked as punishment imposed by the Church. The Jesuit Stairs are one of the most representative examples of Baroque architecture in Dubrovnik. Climbing these stairs, you reach Boškovićeve Poljana (Bošković Square) with the impressive Jesuit Church of Saint Ignatius, built in the 18th century.

As we leave Dubrovnik and head toward Split, we pass by the Trsteno Arboretum, the oldest in Europe, dating back to the 15th century. At the entrance, you can admire two plane trees considered the oldest in the world, over 500 years old. Continuing along the Adriatic Sea, we cross into Bosnia and Herzegovina through the city of Neum, on a 24.5 km stretch where the country has access to the sea.

Split, a UNESCO World Heritage Site, is famously associated with the Palace of Diocletian, a Roman emperor who ruled from 284 to 305. By his order, construction of the palace, made entirely of high-quality marble, began in 293, so it would be ready when he retired from political life in the empire in 305, as he was a Dalmatian. The south side of the palace faces the sea, with its walls ranging from 170 to 200 meters long, and the entire complex covers an area of 38,000 m² (**Photos 136-148**). The Palace holds many historical and architectural wonders. One of them is the Egyptian Sphinx, a stone-carved statue representing the intriguing mythological figure, with the body of a lion and a human head. The presence of this statue in Diocletian's Palace highlights the complex cultural and historical influences that greatly impacted the architecture and art of the time. Emperor Diocletian had connections with Egypt, where he lived for many years before becoming emperor of Rome.

Close to Split is Trogir, the oldest and most charming city in Dalmatia, with a history spanning four thousand years. A UNESCO World Heritage Site, Trogir is entirely walled, with

marble floors. It is a small medieval city located on an island, connected to the mainland by bridges (**Photos 149-153**).

Serbia

Since the end of the First World War, Serbia has been a founding member of most South Slav states, initially as part of the Kingdom of Serbs, Croats, and Slovenes, which was later renamed the Kingdom of Yugoslavia. Over the years, Serbia was part of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia, the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia, and the State Union of Serbia and Montenegro.

The Republic of Serbia is an Eastern European country that borders the Republic of Srpska, Croatia, Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, North Macedonia, Albania, and Montenegro. It has the largest territory among the former Yugoslav republics, covering 88,499 km², with a population of approximately 8.6 million inhabitants.

In March 1999, without the approval of the UN Security Council, NATO, led by the United States, bombed Serbia for 78 days. This was the first military aggression against a sovereign country on the European continent since World War II. There were 38,000 missions, including 11,000 bombing missions, during which the Balkan state was hit with more than 23,000 bombs and missiles. Many of these contained carcinogenic depleted uranium, causing an undetermined number of cancer-related deaths due to radiation exposure.

The bombings left the country in ruins, resulting in thousands of civilian deaths, tens of thousands of injuries, and significant environmental devastation. Shortly afterward, the United States declared the Kosovo region independent of Serbia, where NATO established a military base. Coincidentally, Kosovo's mineral resources play a critical role in the European economy. The region has a diverse geology with exploitable deposits of metals and minerals, including gold, chromium, nickel, aluminum, copper, ferrous metals, and lead-zinc.

In Belgrade, the capital, there are several reminders of the bombings, such as rubble from partially destroyed buildings and signs indicating that the attacks against the Serbian people were carried out by the United States and its allies.

Belgrade, the capital of Serbia and the most important city in the former Yugoslavia, is a must-see for architecture enthusiasts. The city features notable examples of communist-era architecture, particularly Brutalism—a subcategory of the modernist movement known for its minimalist approach, exposed concrete finishes, unconventional shapes, and unique aesthetic. This style can be admired in buildings located in the New Belgrade neighborhood.

One such landmark is Hotel Yugoslavia, located on the Boulevard of Nikola Tesla (**Photo 156**). This historic hotel holds significant cultural and historical importance as one of Belgrade's most iconic landmarks, evoking nostalgia for its role as a luxurious meeting place in Yugoslavia. Built in 1969, it showcases a distinctive Brutalist architectural style and stands prominently on the banks of the Danube River.

In contrast, other buildings in Belgrade date back to the 19th century, reflecting influences from neoclassicism, romanticism, and academic art. Examples include the National Theatre, the Old Palace, the National Assembly, and the National Museum, which also incorporate elements of art nouveau. Neo-Byzantine architecture is evident in structures such as the Vuk Foundation, the old Post Office on Kosovska Street, and sacred buildings like the Church of Saint Mark, inspired by the Gračanica Monastery. The Cathedral of Saint Sava, the largest

Orthodox church in Europe and one of the ten largest churches in the world, is another stunning example of this style (**Photos 157-163**).

The Moskva Hotel is a landmark in Belgrade and one of the Serbian capital's most important architectural jewels, built in the Russian Secession style. The hotel has been under state protection since 1968 as a cultural monument and, since 1979, as a cultural asset of great importance. It was inaugurated by King Petar I Karađorđević in 1908. Throughout its history, this iconic hotel, along with the famous Café Moskva, has welcomed millions of guests, including notable figures such as Albert Einstein, Anna Pavlova, Indira Gandhi, Maxim Gorky, and us—admirers of historical sites—where we enjoyed a coffee and a delicious pie (**Photo 164**).

Walking along Knez Mihailova, a vibrant pedestrian-only street filled with bars, restaurants, and shops, you arrive at Kalemegdan Park, home to the Belgrade Fortress. The fortress, located at the confluence of the Danube and Sava rivers, is a marvel of construction that began in the 2nd century under the Romans. Over the centuries, it endured attacks and devastation by the Goths, Huns, Avars, and Slavs. Today, the site offers breathtaking, panoramic views of the Sava and Danube rivers. Knez Mihailova follows the central grid layout of the ancient Roman city of Singidunum, as one of its main access roads corresponds to the modern street we see today (**Photos 154, 155**).

The Belgrade Ethnographic Museum is well worth a visit, featuring exhibits of traditional costumes, handicrafts, historical photographs, furniture, and various artifacts that reflect the lives of the people from this Balkan region. Another highlight is the famous Skadarlija Street, a pedestrian-only area that breathes art and was revitalized in 1968. Often called the "Serbian Montmartre" due to its artistic past and romantic, bohemian atmosphere, Skadarlija is a must-see.

We also enjoyed a walk along the wide promenade on the banks of the Danube River (**Photo 165**), continuing to its confluence with the Sava River. This is a green and pleasant area that leads to the small town of Zemun, which feels like a charming bohemian neighborhood of Belgrade. Zemun's origins date back to the Roman period. On Gardoš Hill, we climbed a tower built in 1896 that offers stunning views of the Danube (**Photos 166, 167**).

Continuing our journey through the Balkans, between mountains and forests, crossing rivers and valleys, we arrived 230 km from Belgrade at the Studenica Monastery. This historical and architectural monument, built in the 12th century and a UNESCO World Heritage Site, is located in the region of ancient Raška. The monastery belonged to Prince Stefan Nemanja, the founder of the medieval Serbian Empire. Stefan Nemanja was the father of Stefan Prvovenčani, the first king of Serbia, and St. Sava Nemanjić, the first archbishop of Serbia and the founder of the Serbian Orthodox Church.

The monastery offers comfortable accommodations for tourists and excellent cuisine. However, its main attraction is the Orthodox church, adorned with beautiful Byzantine frescoes from the 13th century, which also holds the tombs of Stefan Prvovenčani and his mother, Saint Anastasia (**Photos 168-171**).

Republic of Srpska

The Serbian Republic, or Republika Srpska, is one of the two political entities that make up Bosnia and Herzegovina, the other being the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Its capital is the beautiful city of Banja Luka. Republika Srpska borders Croatia, Bosnia and

Herzegovina, Serbia, and Montenegro, and it is divided into two main regions by the Brčko District: a mountainous western part and a more diverse eastern part, featuring high mountains in the south and fertile, flat land in the north (**Photos 172, 173**).

Višegrad is a historic city situated on the banks of the Drina River. The stone bridge over the Drina, a stunning example of Ottoman architecture built in 1577, serves as a link between Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia (**Photos 174, 175**). During an important historical period, it was located on the main road connecting Sarajevo to Istanbul. The bridge gained further fame thanks to the Yugoslav communist writer Ivo Andrić (1892–1975), winner of the Nobel Prize in Literature, who wrote *The Bridge on the Drina*, a novel that chronicles the history of the city and the bridge from its construction until 1914 [51].

Bosnia and Herzegovina

The Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina is one of the two politically autonomous entities into which the state of Bosnia and Herzegovina is divided. It borders Croatia and the Republic of Srpska and has a small passage to the Adriatic Sea—a 24.5 km stretch between Croatian territory. Half of the population adheres to Christianity (35% follows the Serbian Orthodox Church, and 15% follows Catholicism), while 46% is Muslim.

With the collapse of communism in 1990, Yugoslavia plunged into a wave of nationalism, and the dismemberment of the country was stimulated and orchestrated by the United States and its NATO allies. Still operating with a Cold War mentality, they sought to weaken Serbia, which had long been a strong ally of Moscow and aimed to create a “Greater Serbia,” including the Serb-inhabited parts of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

In 1992, Bosnia and Herzegovina was drawn into a bloody and devastating civil war known as the Bosnian War, during which populations were forcibly removed from regions captured by different nationalities. In 1995, an agreement was signed, leading to the formation of two territorial entities within Bosnia: one under Serbian administration (Republika Srpska) and the other under Bosnian administration (Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina). To this day, the marks of gunfire can still be seen on the walls of buildings in Sarajevo and several other cities (**Photo 188**).

The capital of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina is Sarajevo, a UNESCO World Heritage Site (**Photos 176–191**). The city boasts a beautifully preserved historical and cultural center, Baščaršija, which includes landmarks such as the Gazi Husrev-beg Mosque. Built in the 16th century, this mosque is the largest in Bosnia and Herzegovina and one of the most iconic examples of Ottoman architecture in the Balkans (**Photo 183**). Notably, the Gazi Husrev-beg Mosque became the first mosque in the world to be equipped with electricity and electric lighting in 1898 during the Austro-Hungarian Empire.

The Latin Bridge, also known as the Princip Bridge during the Yugoslav period, is a historic structure spanning the Miljacka River. It holds great historical significance as the site where Archduke Franz Ferdinand of Austria, heir to the Austro-Hungarian throne, and his wife, Sophie, Duchess of Hohenberg, were assassinated on June 28, 1914. This event, carried out by Serbian nationalist Gavrilo Princip, directly triggered the outbreak of World War I.

Kazandžiluk is one of Sarajevo’s oldest and most iconic streets, named after the kazandžijas, or master metalworkers and coppersmiths. These artisans originally produced kettles for the Ottoman army and later expanded their craft to create a variety of copper items for everyday use, such as ewers, pitchers, coffee pots, tabletops, and trays. During Sarajevo’s

Ottoman-era “Golden Age,” coppersmiths produced around a hundred different types of items. Today, Sarajevo’s coppersmiths offer a more limited selection, but Kazandžiluk retains its irresistible charm, continuing to captivate visitors, especially tourists (**Photo 186**).

The landscape between Sarajevo and Mostar is characterized by extensive cultivation of the Blatina grape, a red wine grape variety primarily grown in the Herzegovina region. The 130 km journey between these two beautiful cities is filled with breathtaking scenery. In the canyon of the Neretva River, grapes are cultivated to produce the delicious white wine Žilavka. Additionally, the Bosnian beer Mostarsko Pivo is highly regarded and perhaps one of the best beers among the former Yugoslav countries.

Mostar is renowned for its iconic old bridge (Stari Most), built by Sultan Suleiman the Magnificent (1520–1566) in 1557 over the Neretva River. Located in the historic part of the city, Mostar was a significant center during the Ottoman Empire. The old bridge is a prominent architectural monument and a UNESCO World Heritage Site. It was tragically bombed and destroyed by the Croats on November 9, 1993, but was reconstructed and reopened in 2004.

The Neretva River is regarded as one of the cleanest rivers in Europe. Beyond the old bridge and the crystal-clear river, the old bazaar (Kujundžiluk) is a historic area that preserves traditional craft shops and restaurants. The Koski Mehmed Pasha Mosque, built in 1619 during the Ottoman Empire, is another remarkable landmark and a beautiful visual highlight in the city (**Photos 192–199**).

Montenegro

Montenegro is a small Balkan republic located along the Adriatic Sea, bordered by Albania, Serbia, the Republic of Srpska, and Croatia. The country has just over 600,000 inhabitants, and its capital is Podgorica. Between 1945 and 1991, and again from then until 2003, Montenegro was one of the constituent republics of the Socialist Republic of Yugoslavia and the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia, respectively. From 2003 until June 2006, it was one of the two republics that formed the State of Serbia and Montenegro. Following a referendum, Montenegro declared its independence when just over 50% of the voting population chose separation from Serbia, in alignment with the interests of the European Community and the United States, who had long advocated for the complete dissolution of Yugoslavia and the isolation of Serbia.

However, there are suspicions of fraud surrounding the referendum, as in 1992, a referendum to discuss a union with Serbia saw around 96% of votes in favor of that option. A few years later, Montenegro officially became a NATO member state.

Kotor is a coastal town in Montenegro, a small Balkan country that was once part of the former Yugoslavia. It is located in a secluded area of the Bay of Kotor, one of the most indented parts of the Adriatic Sea, and has a population of around 13,000. The old Mediterranean port of Kotor is surrounded by fortifications built during the Venetian period. Some have referred to it as the southernmost fjord in Europe, though it is actually a ria, a submerged river canyon. Together with the nearly vertical limestone cliffs of Orjen and Lovćen, Kotor and its surrounding area form an impressive landscape. Kotor is part of the World Heritage Site known as the Natural and Cultural-Historical Region of Kotor. The fortified city of Kotor is also listed as a UNESCO World Heritage Site as part of the Venetian Works of Defense from the 16th and 17th centuries. Kotor is one of the most popular tourist destinations in Montenegro due to its well-preserved medieval architecture. In 2019, it welcomed over 250,000 tourists.

The medieval city of Kotor is nestled between rugged mountains, facing the Adriatic Sea and surrounded by centuries-old stone walls. Upon entering the city, you can admire the beautiful Baroque-style clock tower from 1602 and the main Venetian square, which is filled with cafes. The city is truly breathtaking. Looking up, you can see the rugged limestone cliffs of Mount Lovćen. As you wander through the labyrinth of narrow medieval streets, full of museums, shops, bars, and restaurants, you'll notice cats everywhere – hundreds of calm, well-fed felines sitting on the steps of an old church, lounging in comfortable baskets at store entrances, or relaxing in gardens or shaded spots along the walls (**Photos 200–207**).

Montenegrins believe that cats are a symbol of good luck, and many elderly residents of Kotor will tell you they have always loved cats. For many years, nearly every door in homes and businesses has had a cat flap, allowing these furry guests to come and go as they please. Having survived wars, sieges, and earthquakes, the cats have played a key role in helping to protect the town over the years. Kotor, located between the sea and mountains, was once home to many mice, rats, and snakes, making it essential to have cats in the town for protection. Another interesting fact is that Kotor was built by the Venetian Republic, and the symbol of the Venetian Republic is a lion, so the cats have always been respected. There is even a museum dedicated to them – the Cats Museum of Kotor. Cats are so integral to the identity of Kotor that they have taken on a symbolic meaning [52]. If you're a cat lover, a visit to this purrfect haven is a must.

North Macedonia

North Macedonia is a landlocked country, bordered by Serbia, Bulgaria, Greece, and Albania. It has just over 2 million inhabitants, and the capital is Skopje. On June 17, 2018, the Republic of Macedonia and Greece signed an agreement in which the country changed its name to the Republic of North Macedonia. In exchange, Greece lifted its veto on North Macedonia's accession to NATO and the European Union. Entry into the military alliance was almost immediate, but entry into the European Union remains a distant dream for the country.

Geographically, North Macedonia roughly corresponds to the ancient kingdom of Paeonia. In the late 6th century BC, the Achaemenid Persians under Darius the Great conquered Paeonia, incorporating what is now North Macedonia into their vast empire. In 356 BC, Philip II annexed this region into the ancient kingdom of Macedonia, and his son, Alexander the Great, conquered the rest of the area, incorporating it into his empire, reaching as far north as Scupi (modern-day Skopje).

Skopje is a modern city with monumental buildings and statues, many of which date back to the communist period. The Vardar River divides the beautiful city, with bridges connecting the Old Skopje Bazaar, the mosque, the Skopje Fortress Kale, the theater, and the archaeological museum to the modern commercial center. There, you will find the vast Macedonia Square, with a fountain featuring the equestrian statue of Alexander the Great, guarded by statues of lions and Macedonian warriors (**Photos 208–221**).

Skopje's modern center is filled with buildings from the communist era, designed in a style known as brutalist architecture – large, rectangular structures made primarily of concrete – complemented by the enormous Soviet-era bronze statues scattered throughout the city (**Photos 244, 245**).

Among the bridges that cross the Vardar River, the most famous is the Skopje Stone Bridge (**Photos 209, 211**), a masonry arch bridge. It was built by the Serbian Emperor Dušan

Silni in 1346 and is the symbol of the city. The bridge connects two very different parts of Skopje: the predominantly Albanian north and the predominantly Macedonian south.

Among the dozens of fountains scattered throughout Skopje, the highlight is the Fountain of the Mothers of Macedonia, a Soviet-era monument featuring four statues of mothers—one pregnant and others interacting with her young children in the early years of life (**Photos 216, 217**).

The Archaeological Museum of the Republic of North Macedonia (**Photo 210**) is the most significant and oldest museum institution in the country. The museum houses thousands of artifacts from Prehistoric Archaeology, Antiquity, Medieval Archaeology, Numismatics, Anthropology, and the Lapidarium. It was reorganized during the period of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia and is considered one of the seven best museums in Europe, according to the European Museum Academy.

About 50 km from Skopje is Tetovo, the city with the largest concentration of Albanians in all of North Macedonia. The main attraction of Tetovo is the colorful Šarena Džamija mosque, built in 1438 on the banks of the Pena River. It is simply beautiful and unlike traditional mosques, as it features painted walls both inside and out, in a magnificent combination of designs and colors, instead of the traditional ceramic tiles from the Ottoman period (**Photos 222–225**).

Next to this beautiful mosque is the Türbe, a mausoleum dedicated to Hurshida and Mensure, two sisters who financed the construction of the mosque in the 15th century. On the opposite side of the river, in front of the mosque, is the hamam, a Turkish bath from the 16th century, which now serves as a gallery (**Photo 226**). A few hundred meters away is the Arabati Baba Tekke, a spiritual complex associated with Sufism, built in the 16th century. It served as a center for spiritual retreats and offers visitors the opportunity to explore the prayer rooms, dining areas, and accommodations (**Photo 227**).

North Macedonia has several important national parks. Mavrovo National Park is the largest and is located in the west of the country, almost on the border with Albania. The park is stunning, full of lakes, rivers, waterfalls, gorges, dense forests teeming with wildlife, and many mountains, as it is situated in the Balkans (**Photos 228–232**). The highest peak in North Macedonia is Mount Korab, located in Mavrovo, which stands at 2,764 meters. Heading south toward Greece and crossing the Balkans, you will find Lake Ohrid, the deepest lake in the Balkans, at 288 meters deep. It is also one of the oldest lakes in the world, alongside Lake Titicaca and Lake Baikal.

Lake Ohrid takes its name from the city of Ohrid, which was established on the lakeshore hundreds of years ago. This city is the tourist capital of North Macedonia, and the lake, surrounded by several beaches and Byzantine monasteries, is one of the country's major attractions. The lake, which forms the border between North Macedonia and Albania, is listed as a World Heritage Site for its exceptional natural beauty, with the classification extending to its historical and cultural sites.

One such site is Bones Bay (**Photos 228–232**), an archaeological complex located on the coast of Ohrid. It is an authentic reconstruction of a prehistoric settlement. The settlement, over a thousand years old, covered 8,500 square meters. At the time, Lake Ohrid was quite shallow, allowing for the construction of a huge wooden structure on stilts over the water, considered one of the largest prehistoric palaces. There are 24 replicas of prehistoric houses in the settlement, made of wood, straw, and clay, which offer a glimpse into the life of the prehistoric people who once lived there.

Among the historical and architectural attractions of Ohrid is the Orthodox Church of St. John the Theologian (**Photo 242**), built in the 13th century on Kaneo beach. This beautiful church was used to film scenes from the movie *Before the Rain* (original title: *Pred dozhdot*), directed by Macedonian filmmaker Milcho Manchevski. The film won the Golden Lion at the 1994 Venice Film Festival and features a wonderful soundtrack by the Macedonian musical group Anastasia. The Church of Saint Sophia (**Photo 242**) is the oldest in Ohrid, built in the 11th century by Leo, Archbishop of Ohrid, between 1037 and 1056. Leo was one of the negotiators of the Great Schism of the East, which separated the Church into Roman Catholic and Orthodox branches. Before that, the archbishop designed Saint Sophia to represent his theological theses.

Another place of historical and architectural importance in Ohrid is Plaošnik, in Kaneo, an archaeological site and sacred place (**Photo 243**). It was here that Saint Clement of Ohrid, an important figure in Slavic culture, settled. He built a church on the foundations of an older one and founded the first Slavic university. Clement was a disciple of Saints Cyril and Methodius, who created the first Slavic alphabet, the Glagolitic script. The Church of Saints Clement and Panteleimon is a Byzantine church located on a hill known as Plaošnik, overlooking Lake Ohrid (**Photos 244, 245**). The original church is believed to have been built when Saint Clement arrived in Ohrid at the request of Boris I of Bulgaria and restored an old church. The exterior of the church features a large number of finely detailed mosaics.

On the border with Albania, on Lake Ohrid, is the Monastery of Saint Naum (**Photo 240**), a UNESCO World Heritage Site. The route to the monastery is beautiful, with several spots where visitors can take a dip in Lake Ohrid. The monastery itself is magnificent and boasts excellent tourist infrastructure, with areas for sunbathing and swimming, bars, restaurants, bathrooms, picnic areas, and boat trips along the forest streams. The Orthodox Church and monastery were built in the 10th century by Saint Naum (Sveti Naum), who was attributed with healing powers similar to those of the Archangel Michael. For this reason, his tomb in the church remains a pilgrimage site today.

The photos presented in this report were taken by Fabio Rossano Dario and Cristina De Vincenzo, using a cellphone and a Canon PowerShot digital camera.

CONCLUSIONS

Yugoslavia was once one of the most culturally diverse, historically rich, and naturally stunning countries in the world. The six nations that made up this former Socialist Republic each boast unique and compelling qualities for tourism. These include breathtaking natural landscapes traversed by the Balkan Mountains, rivers such as the Danube, and the emerald-green waters of the Adriatic Sea. The scenery is consistently lush, home to a wide variety of plant and animal species, some of which are endemic. The natural environment is adorned with countless rivers, streams, and crystal-clear lakes, often shimmering in emerald blue and connected by cascades and waterfalls.

The cities in these countries are beautiful, clean, and well-organized, with well-preserved historical centers filled with monuments, museums, theaters, and other cultural landmarks, as culture has always been deeply rooted in the lives of the Slavic people. The locals are well-educated, the culture is extraordinarily rich, the cuisine is delightful, the wines and beers are exquisite, and warm hospitality is a constant – whether in Sarajevo, Belgrade, on the shores of

Lake Bled or Lake Ohrid, on a Croatian beach, in a village in Montenegro, or in a monastery deep in Serbia.

Of all the trips we have taken – including three incredible journeys to explore the entirety of former Yugoslavia – this one will undoubtedly remain etched in our memories as the most unforgettable adventure we've ever experienced.

References

- [1] T. Podobnikar. Georeferencing and quality assessment of Josephine survey maps for the mountainous region in the Triglav National Park. *Acta Geodaetica et Geophysica Hungarica* 44(1) (2009) 49-66
- [2] B. Rožič. Perbla and Tolmin formations: Revised Toarcian to Tithonian stratigraphy of the Tolmin Basin (NW Slovenia) and regional correlations. *Bulletin de la Société géologique de France* 180(5) (2009) 411-430
- [3] A. Šmuc, B. Rožič. The Jurassic Prehodavci Formation of the Julian Alps: easternmost outcrops of Rosso Ammonitico in the Southern Alps (NW Slovenia). *Swiss Journal of Geosciences* 103 (2010) 241-255
- [4] A. Carey, D. Smith, S. Welch, M. Zorn, J. Tičar, M. Lipar, B. Komac, B. Lyons. The geochemistry of ice in the Southeastern Alps, Slovenia. *Acta geographica Slovenica* 60(2) (2020) 141-153
- [5] M. Gabrovec, J. Ortar, M. Pavšek, M. Zorn. The Triglav Glacier between the years 1999 and 2012. *Acta geographica Slovenica* 53(2) (2013) 257-293
- [6] A. Šmuc, G. Rožič. Tectonic geomorphology of the Triglav Lakes Valley (easternmost Southern Alps, NW Slovenia). *Geomorphology* 103(4) (2009) 597-604
- [7] M. Buzov. Ancient Settlements along the Sava river. *Histria Antiqua* 20(20) (2011) 355-373
- [8] I. Zelnik, T. Balanč, M.J. Tolman. Diversity and structure of the Tychoplankton diatom community in the Limnocene Spring Zelenci (Slovenia) in relation to environmental factors. *Water* 10(4) (2018) 361-373
- [9] S. Sušnik, P. Kozmus, J. Poklucar, V Meglič. Molecular characterization of indigenous *Apis mellifera carnica* in Slovenia. *Apidologie* 35 (2004) 623-636
- [10] B. Vornam, N. Recarli, O. Gailing. Spatial distribution of genetic variation in a natural beech stand (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) based on microsatellite markers. *Conservation Genetics* 5 (2004) 561-570
- [11] J. Bavcon, B. Ravnjak. Seed banks as a partnership for global plant conservation. *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 57(1) (2014) 3-13
- [12] B.A. Caspers, E.T. Krause, I. Hermanski, C. Wiesbrock, F.W. Kastrup, S. Steinfartz. Developmental costs of yellow colouration in fire salamanders and experiments to test the efficiency of yellow as a warning colouration. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 41(3) (2020) 373-385

- [13] D. Pellitteri-Rosa, J. Martín, P. López, A. Bellati, R. Sacchi, M. Fasola, P. Galeotti. Chemical polymorphism in male femoral gland secretions matches polymorphic coloration in common wall lizards (*Podarcis muralis*). *Chemoecology* 24 (2014) 67-78
- [14] J.F. Schmidtler, W. Böhme. Synonymy and nomenclatural history of the Common or Viviparous Lizard, by this time: *Zootoca vivipara* (Lichtenstein, 1823). *Bonn Zoological Bulletin* 60(2) (2011) 214-228
- [15] M. Adamič. The expanding brown bear population of Slovenia: a chance for bear recovery in the southeastern Alps. *International Conference on Bear Research and Management* 9(2) (1997) 25-29
- [16] C. Randler. Is tail wagging in white wagtails, *Motacilla alba*, an honest signal of vigilance?. *Animal Behaviour* 71 (5) (2006) 1089-1093
- [17] T.A. Wilkin, L.E. King, B.C. Sheldon. Habitat quality, nestling diet, and provisioning behaviour in great tits *Parus major*. *Journal of Avian Biology* 40(2) (2009) 135-145
- [18] M. Metzmacher. Imitations et transmission culturelle dans le chant du Pinson des arbres *Fringilla coelebs*? *Alauda* 84 (2016) 203-220
- [19] L. Božič. Numbers, distribution and nest site characteristics of Jackdaw *Corvus monedula* in Slovenia and its conservation status. *Acrocephalus* 37(170/171) (2016) 123-150
- [20] P. Zduniak. The prey of Hooded Crow (*Corvus cornix* L.) in wetland: Study of damaged egg shells of birds. *Polish Journal of Ecology* 54(3) (2006) 491-498
- [21] J. Böhner, K. Witt. Distribution, abundance and dynamics of the House Sparrow (*Passer domesticus*) in Berlin: a review. *International Studies on Sparrows* 32 (2007) 14-29
- [22] J. Nagy. Phylogeny and evolution of the European Goldfinch (*Carduelis carduelis*) and its allies: a review of the “bird of the year. *Ornis Hungarica* 25(2) (2017) 1-10
- [23] R.J. Safran. Nest-site selection in the barn swallow, *Hirundo rustica*: What predicts seasonal reproductive success? *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 84(11) (2006) 1533-1539
- [24] G. Balázs, B. Lewarne, G. Herczeg. Extreme site fidelity of the olm (*Proteus anguinus*) revealed by a long-term capture-mark-recapture study. *Journal of Zoology* 311 (2020) 99-105
- [25] M. Vurnek, A. Brozinčević, Ž. Rendulić, K. Miculinić, V. Vukadin, O. Škunca. Management zonation and its implementation at a UNESCO world heritage site: a case study for the Plitvice Lakes National Park, Croatia. *European Journal of Environmental Sciences* 9(2) (2019) 87-96
- [26] F.R. Dario, M.C.V. De Vincenzo. The unsurpassable natural beauty of the Plitviče Lakes National Park, in Croatia. *The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin* 16 (2022) 1-68
- [27] A. Pentecost, H. Viles. A review and reassessment of travertine classification. *Geographie Physique et Quaternaire* 48(3) (1994) 305-314

- [28] M. Miliša, I. Habdija, B. Primc-Habdija, I. Radanović, R.M. Kepčija. The role of flow velocity in the vertical distribution of particulate organic matter on moss-covered travertine barriers of the Plitvice Lakes (Croatia). *Hydrobiologia* 553 (2006) 231-243
- [29] H.S. Chafetz, R.L. Folk. Travertines: depositional morphology and bacterially constructed constituent. *Journal of Sedimentary Petrology* 54 (1984) 289-316
- [30] H.S. Chafetz, D. Srdoč, N. Horvatinčić. Early diagenesis of Plitvice Lakes waterfall and barrier travertine deposits. *Géographie physique et Quaternaire* 48 (1994) 247-255
- [31] A. Jazbec, K. Segotić, M. Ivanković, H. Marjanović, S. Perić. Ranking of European beech provenances in Croatia using statistical analysis and analytical hierarchy process. *Forestry* 80 (2007) 151-162
- [32] I. Tikvić, Z. Seletković, D. Ugarković, S. Posavec, Ž. Španjol. Dieback of Silver Fir (*Abies alba* Mill.) on Northern Velebit (Croatia). *Periodicum Biologorum* 110(2) (2008) 137-143
- [33] D. Dobrowolska, A. Bončina, R. Klumpp. Ecology and silviculture of silver fir (*Abies alba* Mill.): A review. *Journal of Forest Research* 22 (2017) 326-335
- [34] M. Čater, J. Diaci, D. Roženberger. Gap size and position influence variable response of *Fagus sylvatica* L. and *Abies alba* Mill. *Forest Ecology and Management* 325 (2014) 128-135
- [35] M. Dinarvand. A taxonomic revision of *Utricularia* (Lentibulariaceae) for aqua flora of Iran Iranian. *Journal of Botany* 18 (2012) 191-195
- [36] M. Sielezniew, R. Rutkowski, D. Ponikwicka-Tyszko, M. Ratkiewicz, I. Dziekańska, G. Śvitra. Differences in genetic variability between two ecotypes of the endangered myrmecophilous butterfly *Phengaris* (= *Maculinea*) *alcon*: the setting of conservation priorities. *Insect Conservation and Diversity* 5(3) (2012) 223-236
- [37] I. Buj, M. Čaleta, Z. Marčić, D. Zanella, P. Mustafić. The fish of the Plitvice Lakes - A Wealth of Simplicity. *Plitvice Lakes* (2023) 317-342
- [38] J.F. Schmidtler, W. Böhme. Synonymy and nomenclatural history of the Common or Viviparous Lizard, by this time: *Zootoca vivipara* (Lichtenstein, 1823). *Bonn Zoological Bulletin* 60(2) (2011) 214-228
- [39] J. Serra-Cobo, M. Lopez-Roig, T. Marques-Bonet, E. Lahuerta. Rivers as possible landmarks in the orientation flight of *Miniopterus schreibersii*. *Acta Theriologica* 45(3) (2000) 347-352
- [40] M. Uhrin, S. Boldogh, S. Bücs, M. Paunović, E. Miková, M. Juhász, I. Csösz, P. Estók, M. Fulín, P. Gombkötő, C. Jéré, L. Barti, B. Karapandža, Š. Matis, Z.L. Nagy, F. Szodoray-Parádi, P. Benda Revision of the occurrence of *Rhinolophus euryale* in the Carpathian region, Central Europe. *Vespertilio* 16 (2012) 289-328
- [41] I. Pavlinić, M. Đaković. The greater horseshoe bat, *Rhinolophus Ferrumequinum* in Croatia: Present status and research recommendations. *Natura Croatica* 19(2) (2010) 339-356

- [42] N. Bunnefeld, J.D.C. Linnell, J. Odden, M.A.J. Van Duijn, R. Andersen. Risk taking by Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in a human-dominated landscape: Effects of sex and reproductive status. *Journal of Zoology* 270(1) (2206) 31-39
- [43] H. Valdmann, E. Moks, H. Talvik. Helminth fauna of Eurasian lynx (*Lynx lynx*) in Estonia. *Journal of Wildlife Diseases* 40(2) (2004) 356-360
- [44] S. Mancinelli, L. Boitani, P. Ciucci. Determinants of home range size and space use patterns in a protected wolf (*Canis lupus*) population in the central Apennines, Italy. *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 96(8) (2018) 828-838
- [45] D. O'Mahony, C. O'Reilly, P. Turner. Pine Marten (*Martes martes*) distribution and abundance in Ireland: a cross-jurisdictional analysis using non-invasive genetic survey techniques. *Mammalian Biology* 77 (2012) 351-357
- [46] A. Frković, R.L. Ruff, L. Cicnjak, Đ. Huber. Brown bear mortality during 1946-85 in Gorski Kotar, Yugoslavia. *Proceedings of the Bear Workshop of the International Conference on Bear Research and Management* 7 (1987) 87-92
- [47] J. Kusak, Đ. Huber. Brown bear habitat quality in Gorski Kotar, Croatia. *Ursus* 10 (1998) 281-291
- [48] H. Roth, Đ. Huber. Diel activity of brown bears in Plitvice Lakes National Park, Yugoslavia. *Proceedings of the Bear Workshop of the International Conference on Bear Research and Management* 6 (1986) 177-181
- [49] E. Kalisińska, M. Palczewska-Komsa. Teeth of the red fox *Vulpes vulpes* (L., 1758) as a bioindicator in studies on fluoride pollution. *Acta Theriologica* 56 (2011) 343-351
- [50] M. Sindičić, T. Gomerčić, J. Kusak, V. Slijepčević, Đ. Huber, A. Frković. Mortality in the Eurasian lynx population in Croatia during the 40 years. *Mammalian Biology* 81(3) (2016) 290-294
- [51] H.R. Cooper Jr. The Structure of The Bridge on the Drina. *The Slavic and East European Journal* 27(3) (1983) 365-373
- [52] F.R. Dario, M.C.V. De Vincenzo. The cities and the guardians of the night. *The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin* 23 (2024) 1-64

Appendix

Photo 1. Dragon Bridge (Zmajski Most) is the symbol of Ljubljana, Slovenia.

Photo 2. Detail of one of the dragons on the Dragon Bridge in Ljubljana, Slovenia.

Photo 3. Ljubljana is located on the banks of the Ljubljanica River, which is a tributary of the Sava River, one of the main tributaries on the right bank of the Danube River.

Photo 4. The Ljubljanica River passes through the center of Ljubljana in the form of a canal ...

Photo 5. ... and is crossed by beautiful and historic bridges, such as the Triple Bridge.

Photo 6. Prešeren Square, the most important square in Ljubljana, is named after the Slovenian Romantic poet France Prešeren.

Photo 7. Ljubljana, Slovenia.

Photo 8. Ljubljana, Slovenia.

Photo 9. Ljubljana Castle.

Photo 10. Ljubljana Castle Museum: Puppets.

Photo 11. Metelkova Mesto, a small town in Ljubljana, is a self-declared 'Autonomous Culture Zone.'

Photo 12. Details from the facade of a residence in Metelkova Mesto, Ljubljana.

Photo 13. The Natural History Museum of Slovenia, in Ljubljana: skeleton of a woolly mammoth (*Mammuthus primigenius*), the last species of mammoth, extinct about 5,000 years ago.

Photo 14. The Natural History Museum of Slovenia, in Ljubljana: skeleton of a cave bear (*Ursus spelaeus*), which lived in Europe during the Pleistocene and disappeared around 10,000 years ago, at the end of the last Ice Age.

Photo 15. The Natural History Museum of Slovenia, in Ljubljana: the brown bear (*Ursus arctos*), a large bear native to Eurasia and North America.

Photo 16. The Natural History Museum of Slovenia, in Ljubljana: the griffon vulture (*Gyps fulvus*) is a vulture that occurs in the mountains of southern Europe, southwest Asia, and Africa.

Photo 17. Entrance to the Slovenian Parliament in Ljubljana, which houses the National Assembly of the Republic of Slovenia, with sculptures created by Drago Tršar.

Photo 18. Ljubljana: The main monument in Revolution Square is the Monument to the Revolution, opened in 1975 and created by Drago Tršar.

Photo 19. Bled, located approximately 50 km from Ljubljana, is known for its beautiful lake surrounded by the Julian Alps, forests, and a medieval castle.

Photo 20. Lake Bled surrounds Bled Island, which has a few buildings, the main one being the pilgrimage church dedicated to the Assumption of Mary, built in the 17th century.

Photo 21. We circled Lake Bled along a 6 km trail, with beautiful views of the island and the castle.

Photo 22. Around Lake Bled, Slovenia.

Photo 23. Bled Castle is the oldest in Slovenia and began to be built in the 11th century, on a 130-meter-high cliff on the banks of the lake.

Photo 24. From the castle, the view of the lake is incredible. Lake Bled is considered by some to be the most beautiful lake in the world.

Photo 25. The beautiful medieval city of Radovljica is the world capital of honey, produced by Carniolan bees (*Apis mellifera carnica*), a species endemic to Slovenia.

Photo 26. Not far from Bled is the picturesque village of Spodnja Sorica, considered the most beautiful in Slovenia, where the Impressionist painter Ivan Grohar (1867-1911) was born.

Photo 27. Škofja Loka, Slovenia.

Photo 28. Škofja Loka, a UNESCO World Heritage site, is considered one of the most beautiful medieval cities in Slovenia.

Photo 29. Triglav National Park (Triglavski Narodni Park in Slovene) is Slovenia's largest protected area.

Photo 30. The Soča is an Alpine river that flows through western Slovenia and passes through beautiful cities like Kanal ob Soči.

Photo 31. The Soča River is the “emerald beauty” that inspired the poet Simon Gregorčič to write his best-known poem, considered one of the masterpieces of Slovene poetry.

Photo 32. The Sava Dolinka is a river that rises at the Zelenci Pools near Kranjska Gora. It is one of the main tributaries of the Sava River.

Photo 33. Mount Triglav (2,864 m) is the highest summit of the Julian Alps and of Slovenia. To Slovenians, it represents a prime national symbol.

Photo 34. Mount Triglav, stylized, is the central element of the Republic of Slovenia's coat of arms, along with three golden stars, stemming from the coat of arms of the Counts of Celje, and the sea, present in the national flag.

Photo 35. Triglav National Park is an area of varied relief, manifested in a wealth of natural forms.

Photo 36. The Planica Valley is a real tourist magnet, not only for mountaineering and climbing but also for family-friendly cycling and hiking.

Photo 37. Lake Bohinj, which lies in the heart of Triglav National Park, is the largest natural lake in Slovenia, nestled at the foot of unspoiled mountains and mountaintops.

Photo 38. Apart from the lake itself, St. John the Baptist Church is the hallmark of Bohinj. It is one of the finest examples of Slovenian medieval architecture and mural painting. This postcard-worthy medieval church and stone bridge are over 700 years old, spanning time periods from Romanticism to Baroque.

Photo 39. Zelenci Springs is a nature reserve near the town of Kranjska Gora, in the far northwestern corner of Slovenia. It is the source of the Sava Dolinka River.

Photo 40. The white butterbur (*Petasites albus*) is a plant species in the family Asteraceae. It is native to Central Europe and the Caucasus. It prefers damp soils in deciduous forests, mountain pastures, and streamsides.

Photo 41. Lake Jasna is guarded by a statue of a Zlatorog (golden horn), the legendary chamois of Mount Triglav. The work is by Slovenian sculptor Stojan Batič.

Photo 42. Wooden paths by the riverside in the Vintgar Gorge, Triglav National Park.

Photo 43. Vintgar Gorge, Triglav National Park.

Photo 44. Wooden walkway with a handrail in the Vintgar Gorge.

Photo 45. Vintgar Gorge, Triglav National Park.

Photo 46. Zadlaščica River Canyon, Tolmin Gorges, Triglav National Park.

Photo 47. Slovenia is the home of the Carniolan honeybee, an indigenous Slovenian bee. Painted beehive panels are a characteristic feature of Slovenian beekeeping and an expression of folk art.

Photo 48. Detail of the emerald-green Kozjak stream.

Photo 49. Detail of the emerald-green Kozjak stream.

Photo 50. The mystical view of the rocky amphitheater with the green pool and the white beam of water at the Kozjak Waterfall.

Photo 51. The beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) is one of the predominant tree species in Triglav National Park.

Photo 52. The *Iris sibirica* subsp. *erirrhiza* can only be found in very dry habitats in Slovenian (and Croatian) Istria, the Kras region, Mount Nanos, and possibly Mount Kojca, as well as several other dry mountainous habitats.

Photo 53. *Podarcis muralis* is a species of lizard with a wide distribution in Europe. It prefers rocky environments, including urban settings, where it can scurry between rocks and rubble.

Photo 54. *Podarcis muralis* has scales that are highly variable in color and pattern. Its coloration is typically brownish or greyish but may occasionally have a greenish hue.

Photo 55. The common chaffinch (*Fringilla coelebs*, ♂) is a small and widespread passerine bird in the finch family. The male is brightly colored, featuring a blue-grey cap and rust-red underparts. It has a strong voice and sings from perches to attract mates.

Photo 56. The great tit (*Parus major*) is a widespread and common species throughout Europe. It is predominantly insectivorous and is a familiar bird often found in urban parks and gardens.

Photo 57. Postojna Cave is the largest tourist cave in Europe, the most visited cave in the world, and the birthplace of modern caving, thanks to the proteus salamander (*Proteus anguinus*).

Photo 58. Close to Postojna Cave is the incredible Predjama Castle, built in the 13th century and set into a mountain on a 123-meter cliff.

Photo 59. Koper, Slovenia.

Photo 60. Koper, Slovenia.

Photo 61. Koper, Slovenia.

Photo 62. Road between Koper and Portorož.

Photo 63. The Slovenian coastline is relatively narrow and includes the regions of Goriška and Slovenian Istria along the Adriatic Sea.

Photo 64. Piran is a beautiful city on the Slovenian coast, dating back to the Roman period.

Photo 65. Piran, Slovenia.

Photo 66. Piran offers incredible views of the Adriatic coast.

Photo 67. Sečovlje Salina, located in the Sečovlje Salina Nature Park, is the oldest active salt mine in the world, with the earliest record being a decree by Charlemagne from 804.

Photo 68. Sečovlje Salina Nature Park, Slovenia.

Photo 69. Celje, the ancient Celeia of the Romans...

Photo 70. ... is located at the confluence of four rivers, which gives it strategic importance.

Photo 71. In the central square of Celje, Slovenia, there is a statue honoring the remarkable Alma Karlin, who was born and died in this city and was the first woman to travel around the world.

Photo 72. Ptuj, the ancient Roman Petóvio, is very charming, overlooking the Drava River, with colorful buildings, a beautiful tower, and a stunning medieval castle from the 12th century.

Photo 73. Ptuj, Slovenia.

Photo 74. Ptuj, Slovenia.

Photo 75. Ptuj, Slovenia.

Photo 76. Ptuj, Slovenia.

Photo 77. Maribor is one of the most beautiful cities in Europe, very welcoming, with medieval buildings, squares, and lush gardens.

Photo 78. Main Square in Maribor, Slovenia.

Photo 79. Main Square in Maribor, Slovenia.

Photo 80. Maribor, Slovenia.

Photo 81. Maribor, Slovenia.

Photo 82. Maribor, Slovenia.

Photo 83. The Drava River in Maribor is crossed by the Old Bridge, which is entirely made of iron and painted red. It was built in 1913.

Photo 84. The Old Vine House and the vine with nearly 500 years of historical record.

Photo 85. This vine has nearly 500 years of historical record, surviving the wars and plagues that devastated Europe in recent centuries.

Photo 86. Castle Square in Maribor: a detail of the bronze monument, created by sculptor Slavko Tihec, which was built in honor of the 667 Slovenian communists who were killed by German forces during World War II.

Photo 87. The Maribor Botanical Garden.

Photo 88. The Maribor Botanical Garden.

Photo 89. The Maribor Botanical Garden: a detail of the tomb from an ancient Iron Age cemetery.

Photo 90. Church of Saint Mark in Zagreb, dating back to the 13th century, featuring a colorful tiled roof.

Photo 91. Zagreb, Croatia.

Photo 92. A pedestrian tunnel connecting two neighborhoods in Zagreb, Croatia.

Photo 93. The historic part of Zagreb, including the Upper Town and Kaptol, can be accessed by funicular.

Photo 94. The Lotrščak Tower, dating back to the 13th century, is one of the best-preserved buildings from the city's ancient defense system. Every day at noon sharp, a cannon is fired from the top of the tower, a tradition that began in the 19th century.

Photo 95. Zagreb, Croatia.

Photo 96. Zagreb, Croatia.

Photo 97. Zagreb, Croatia.

Photo 98. Zagreb, Croatia.

Photo 99. Zagreb, Croatia.

Photo 100. Botanical Garden of Zagreb: the Gardener's House (currently the Garden's management building).

Photo 101. The Croatian National Theatre in Zagreb, a neo-Baroque architectural marvel that opened in 1895, is the symbol of Marshal Tito Square.

Photo 102. Wooden plank walkway in Plitviče Lakes National Park. The wooden boardwalk stretches for dozens of miles.

Photo 103. Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 104. Autumn leaf colors, in various shades of yellow, orange, red, purple, and brown, are among the attractions of Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 105. The Veliki Prštavci waterfall at the Upper Lakes.

Photo 106. Autumn leaf colors, in various shades of yellow, orange, red, purple, and brown, are among the attractions of Plitviče Lakes National Park.

Photo 107. Bog habitats and their vegetation in Croatia, including those in the park, are relics of the glacial period.

Photo 108. Waterfall near Gradinsko Lake.

Photo 109. A barrier between Gavanovac Lake and Kaluderovac Lake.

Photo 110. Veliki Slap, also known as the Great Waterfall.

Photo 111. The European chub (*Squalius cephalus*) is found in clean water. Notice the clarity and transparency of the water.

Photo 112. The Mallard (*Anas platyrhynchos*) is the most recognized waterfowl in the world. They most often prefer wetlands, where the waters support large amounts of floating, emergent, and submerged vegetation, as well as many aquatic invertebrates on which mallards feed.

Photo 113. The robin (*Erithacus rubecula*) inhabits farmland and woodland, as well as gardens and parks in towns and cities. Its diet consists of seeds, fruits, insects, worms, and other invertebrates.

Photo 114. Dubrovnik, Croatia, "the Pearl of the Adriatic".

Photo 115. Detail of the walls of Dubrovnik, Croatia.

Photo 116. Detail of the walls of Dubrovnik, Croatia.

Photo 117. The Tower of Minčeta, the highest point of the walls of Dubrovnik.

Photo 118. The fortified city of Dubrovnik, a UNESCO World Heritage site and formerly the Republic of Ragusa, rightfully deserves the title "the Pearl of the Adriatic."

Photo 119. The Lovrijenac Fortress is a symbol of resilience for the people of Dubrovnik, an important structure that protected the city for hundreds of years.

Photo 120. Dubrovnik, overlooking the Adriatic Sea, is a city surrounded by walls and fortifications built between the 13th and 16th centuries...

Photo 121. ... and can walk almost 2 km along the wall, enjoying incredible views of the sea and the city.

Photo 122. Dubrovnik, Croatia.

Photo 123. Dubrovnik, Croatia.

Photo 124. The coast of Croatia is recognized as one of the most beautiful places in the world, with landscapes colored by the turquoise-blue sea, home to paradisiacal islands...

Photo 125. ... beautiful historic cities with impressive architecture, all in perfect harmony.

Photo 126. Dubrovnik, Croatia.

Photo 127. The Franciscan Church, Dubrovnik, Croatia.

Photo 128. Dubrovnik, Croatia.

Photo 129. A rest stop and some pomegranate juice.

Photo 130. Pomegranate and grape, two fruits that are very common in Croatia.

Photo 131. The Jesuit Stairs, which became famous in the Game of Thrones series during the "Walk of Shame."

Photo 132. Climbing the Jesuit Stairs, you reach Boškoviće Poljana (Bošković Square), home to the impressive Jesuit Church of Saint Ignatius, built in the 18th century.

Photo 133. Dubrovnik, Croatia.

Photo 134. The Luža Square Clock Tower is one of the most iconic monuments in Dubrovnik.

Photo 135. Dubrovnik, Croatia.

Photo 136. Split, a UNESCO World Heritage Site, is known for the Palace of Diocletian, built by the Roman emperor who ruled from 284 to 305.

Photo 137. Split, Croatia.

Photo 138. The Cathedral of Saint Domnius was built by reusing the structure of the old Mausoleum of Diocletian in Split, Croatia.

Photo 139. Split, Croatia.

Photo 140. Split, Croatia.

Photo 141. A detail of the floor of Emperor Diocletian's palace in Split, Croatia.

Photo 142. A detail of an Egyptian sphinx from Emperor Diocletian's palace in Split, Croatia.

Photo 143. A detail of an Egyptian sphinx from Emperor Diocletian's palace in Split, Croatia.

Photo 144. Split, Croatia.

Photo 145. Split, Croatia.

Photo 146. Split, Croatia.

Photo 147. Split, Croatia.

Photo 148. The underground galleries of Diocletian's Palace in Split, Croatia.

Photo 149. Trogir, the oldest and most charming city in Dalmatia, has four thousand years of history. Entirely walled, with marble floors, it is a small medieval city located on an island connected to the mainland by bridges.

Photo 150. Trogir, Croatia.

Photo 151. Trogir, Croatia.

Photo 152. Trogir, Croatia.

Photo 153. Trogir, Croatia.

Photo 154. Following Knez Mihailova, a vibrant pedestrian-only street in Belgrade filled with bars, restaurants, and shops, you arrive at Kalemegdan Park.

Photo 155. Kalemegdan Park is home to the Belgrade Fortress, located at the confluence of the Danube and Sava rivers. This marvel of construction dates back to the 2nd century, when it was initiated by the Romans.

Photo 156. The Hotel Yugoslavia is a historic hotel in Belgrade, built in 1969. It features a distinctive Brutalist architectural style and is situated on the banks of the Danube.

Photo 157. Belgrade, Serbia.

Photo 158. Belgrade, Serbia.

Photo 159. Belgrade, Serbia.

Photo 160. The National Assembly of the Republic of Serbia, located in Belgrade.

Photo 161. National Museum of Belgrade.

Photo 162. St. Mark's Orthodox Church in Belgrade, Serbia.

Photo 163. The Cathedral of Saint Sava in Belgrade is the largest Orthodox church in Europe and one of the ten largest churches in the world.

Photo 164. The Moskva Hotel is a landmark in Belgrade and one of the Serbian capital's most significant architectural jewels, built in the Russian Secession style.

Photo 165. A view of the Danube River in Belgrade, Serbia.

Photo 166. On Gardoš Hill, in the small town of Zemun near Belgrade, the tower, built in 1896, offers views of the Danube.

Photo 167. A view of the Danube River in Belgrade, Serbia.

Photo 168. Crossing the Balkans toward the Studeniča Monastery in Serbia.

Photo 169. Studeniča Monastery, Serbia.

Photo 170. Studeniča Monastery, Serbia

Photo 171. A detail of archaeological remains from Studeniča Monastery, Serbia.

Photo 172. Crossing the Balkans, on the border between Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Photo 173. Crossing the Balkans, on the border between Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Photo 174. Višegrad is a historic city on the banks of the Drina River. The stone bridge over the Drina, a magnificent example of Ottoman architecture, was built in 1577 and serves as the link between Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia.

Photo 175. The Višegrad Bridge also became famous through the writer Ivo Andrić, who wrote *The Bridge on the Drina*, a novel that tells the story of the city and the bridge from the time of its construction until 1914.

Photo 176. Sarajevo's town hall building, Vijećnica, in neo-Moorish style, has been restored and reopened as a museum and library.

Photo 177. Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Photo 178. The place where Archduke Franz Ferdinand of Austria, presumptive heir to the throne of the Austro-Hungarian Empire, and his wife Sofia, Duchess of Hohenberg, were assassinated.

Photo 179. A Gräf & Stift vehicle similar to the one driven by Archduke Franz Ferdinand of Austria on the day of his assassination in Sarajevo. The vehicle is parked near the scene of the murder.

Photo 180. Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Photo 181. The Gazi Husrev Bey Mausoleum in Sarajevo.

Photo 182. The minaret of the Gazi Husrev-beg Mosque, built in the 16th century, which is the largest mosque in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Photo 183. The historic ruins of Tašlihan, with the old clock tower and the minaret of the Gazi Husrev-beg Mosque in the background, in Sarajevo.

Photo 184. Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Photo 185. Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Photo 186. Kazandžiluk is one of Sarajevo's oldest and most recognizable streets, where tourists can purchase beautiful handcrafted copper pieces.

Photo 187. On a street in Sarajevo, in the company of the greatest inventor of all time, Serbian engineer Nikola Tesla.

Photo 188. Many houses in Sarajevo still bear holes in the walls, a testament to the Bosnian War.

Photo 189. Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Photo 190. Urban transport in Sarajevo.

Photo 191. In Sarajevo, places that sell pomegranate juice are very common.

Photo 192. Between Sarajevo e Mostar, there are stunning landscapes.

Photo 193. Mostar and the Neretva River.

Photo 194. Mostar was a very important city during the Ottoman Empire.

Photo 195. The Old Bridge (Stari Most) of Mostar, Herzegovina.

Photo 196. Mostar, Herzegovina.

Photo 197. A view of Mostar, with the Neretva River and the Koski-Mehmed Pasha Mosque in the background.

Photo 198. Mostar is famous for its Old Bridge (Stari Most), built by Sultan Suleiman the Magnificent in 1557, over the Neretva River.

Photo 199. Koski-Mehmed Pasha Mosque, in Mostar.

Photo 200. Kotor is a coastal town in Montenegro, a small Balkan country that was part of the former Yugoslavia.

Photo 201. Kotor is located in a secluded part of the Bay of Kotor, one of the most indented areas of the Adriatic Sea.

Photo 202. Together with the nearly overhanging limestone cliffs of Orjen and Lovćen, Kotor and its surrounding area form an impressive landscape.

Photo 203. As you enter Kotor, you can see the beautiful Baroque-style clock tower from 1602.

Photo 204. Kotor is one of the most popular tourist destinations in Montenegro, known for its well-preserved medieval architecture.

Photo 205. The historic town of Kotor is home to hundreds of stray cats, who are cared for and adored by both locals and visitors alike.

Photo 206. Kotor, in Montenegro, is one of the best-preserved medieval towns on the Adriatic coast.

Photo 207. We consider the city of Kotor, in Montenegro, to be the ultimate cat paradise in the world.

Photo 208. A view of the Vardar River with the Skopje Fortress Kale in the background, North Macedonia.

Photo 209. A view of the Vardar River with the Stone Bridge and the Archaeological Museum in the background, North Macedonia.

Photo 210. The Archaeological Museum of the Republic of North Macedonia, in neoclassical style.

Photo 211. The Skopje Stone Bridge is one of the city's most iconic landmarks.

Photo 212. Macedonia Square, Skopje, with the fountain featuring the equestrian statue of Alexander the Great.

Photo 213. The fountain with the equestrian statue of Alexander the Great, guarded by statues of lions and Macedonian warriors.

Photo 214. Macedonia Square, Skopje.

Photo 215. Macedonian National Theatre, Skopje.

Photo 216. Fountain of the Mothers of Macedonia, Skopje.

Photo 217. A detail of the statues from the Fountain of the Mothers of Macedonia, Skopje.

Photo 218. One of the most characteristic places in Skopje is the Old Skopje Bazaar. In the background, you can see the minaret of the Mustafa Pasha Mosque, built in 1492.

Photo 219. Skopje Fortress Kale, North Macedonia.

Photo 220. A detail of Soviet monuments present in the squares of Skopje, North Macedonia.

Photo 221. A detail of Soviet monuments present in the squares of Skopje, North Macedonia.

Photo 222. Colorful Šarena Džamija Mosque in Tetovo, North Macedonia.

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Photo 224. Colorful Šarena Džamija Mosque in Tetovo, North Macedonia.

Photo 225. The interior of the colorful Šarena Džamija Mosque in Tetovo is known for its vibrant and intricate designs.

Photo 226. The Hamam, a 16th-century Turkish bath that is now used as a gallery, in Tetovo, North Macedonia.

Photo 227. Arabati Baba Tekke, a spiritual complex popular in Sufi Islam, was built in the 16th century, Tetovo, North Macedonia.

Photo 228. Mavrovo National Park, North Macedonia.

Photo 229. Mavrovo National Park, North Macedonia.

Photo 230. Mavrovo National Park, North Macedonia.

Photo 231. The Balkan Mountains, on the border between North Macedonia and Albania.

Photo 232. The Balkan Mountains, on the border between North Macedonia and Albania.

Photo 233. Lake Ohrid, the deepest lake in the Balkans at 288 meters deep, is also one of the oldest lakes in the world, alongside Lake Titicaca and Lake Baikal.

Photo 234. Lake Ohrid, surrounded by several beaches and Byzantine monasteries, is one of North Macedonia's biggest attractions.

Photo 235. Lake Ohrid forms the border between North Macedonia and Albania.

Photo 236. Bones Bay is an archaeological complex located on the shore of Lake Ohrid. It is an authentic reconstruction of a prehistoric settlement ...

Photo 237. ... At that time, Lake Ohrid was quite shallow, allowing the construction of a large wooden structure on stilts over the water, which is considered one of the largest prehistoric palaces.

Photo 238. There are 24 copies of prehistoric houses in the settlement, made of wood, straw, and clay, which provide insight into the life of the prehistoric people who lived in this community.

Photo 239. A detail of Bones Bay, located on the shore of Lake Ohrid, North Macedonia.

Photo 240. On the border with Albania, along Lake Ohrid, is the Monastery of Saint Naum.

Photo 241. The church of Saint Sophia is the oldest in Ohrid, North Macedonia, built in the 11th century by Leo, Archbishop of Ohrid, between 1037 and 1056.

Photo 242. A detail of the Orthodox Church of St. John the Theologian at Kaneo (13th century), in Ohrid, where scenes from Milcho Manchevski's film *Before the Rain* were filmed.

Photo 243. The ruins of Plaošnik in Ohrid, North Macedonia.

Photo 244. Church of Saints Clement and Panteleimon in Ohrid, North Macedonia.

Photo 245. An icon from the Church of Saints Clement and Panteleimon in Ohrid, North Macedonia.